

EFFECTS OF CARBON NANOTUBE CONTENTS ON GLASS TRANSITION OF EPOXY MATRIX COMPOSITES: ROLE OF INTERPHASE REGION

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ABSTRACT

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation for carbon nanotubes (CNTs) reinforced cross-linked epoxy matrix composites were conducted to study effects of CNT contents on the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the composites. The density, Connolly volume fraction, mean squared displacement and radial distribution function of the composites with 5.7 wt%, 10.9 wt% and 15.5 wt% CNTs were investigated, respectively, and T_g s of the CNTs/epoxy composites were predicted based on the calculated data. Results showed that the T_g s are 505.5 K, 454.4 K and 442.9 K, respectively, compared with 445.7 K for the neat epoxy resin. It can be seen that with CNTs embedded into the epoxy, T_g of the composites increased remarkably at lower CNT contents. However, the T_g s decreased as the CNT contents increased, and T_g of the composites with 15.5 wt% CNTs is even lower than that of the neat epoxy resin. It suggested that the poor interfacial interactions at the interface between CNTs and epoxy lead to a more compressible interphase region between the CNTs and the bulk epoxy matrix.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are used as an ideal reinforcement for epoxy resin, which have attracted great interest in the field of advanced composites. These composites are expected to possess good mechanical properties, excellent electrical and high thermal conductivities [1, 2]. However, the application of CNTs was limited by poorer than theoretically expected enhancement in practice, which had been attributed to various factors. The CNTs reinforced polymer matrix composites are composed of CNTs, polymer matrix and the interphase region between them [3, 4]. It has been proved that the characteristic of the interphase region is a key factor that affects the properties of the composites [5, 6].

The glass transition temperature (T_g) is a key character to evaluate the thermal properties of the composites, which is corresponding to the motion of polymer chain segments [7]. Because of comparable dimensions of the CNTs with polymer chain segments, motions of the polymer chain segments in the composites are supposed to be restricted, restrained, hindered or limited significantly by the embedded CNTs. This mechanism of CNT-polymer-chain-segments interaction is expected to change the T_g . T_g of the composites varied with contents [3], functionalization [8-10] and dispersion states [11-13] of the embedded CNTs, which would change the interfacial interactions between the CNTs and the polymer significantly. Much investigation on the electrical and thermal conductivities showed that these characters increased slowly before the CNT contents increased to the threshold, followed by a sharply rise, where the CNT crosslink network was believed to built [14, 15]. However, there went to no agreement on the effect of CNTs on T_g of the composites [16, 17], let alone the effect of CNT contents.

In practice, contents of CNTs in the composites were usually very low because of the high tendency to form bundles [4, 18, 19], which was an obstacle for the investigation on the effects of CNT contents on the T_g experimentally. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation can not only provide the T_g value prior to sample preparation, but also present the motion of polymer chain segments as well as the properties of the interphase region between the polymer and the CNTs, which would be helpful to understand the glass transition behavior of the composites.

In this study, the matrix was cross-linked epoxy molecules based on the epoxy monomers bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA) cured by diaminodiphenylmethane (DDM). With different CNT molecules embedded into cross-linked epoxy resin network, models of the composites with different CNT contents were established. The density, Connolly volume fraction (CVF), mean squared displacement (MSD) and radial distribution function (RDF) were calculated, and T_g s of the CNTs/epoxy were predicted based on the calculated data. Motion of the chain segments in the glass transition process were analyzed [20], attempting to establish relationships between CNT contents and glass transition behavior of the composites.

2 MODELS AND SIMULATION METHODOLOGY

2.1 Models

In order to investigate effects of CNT contents on glass transition of the epoxy matrix composites, models for 1, 2 and 3 CNT molecule(s) embedded in the cross-linked epoxy composites were constructed, respectively. The three composite systems were corresponding to the weight ratios of 5.7 %、10.9 % and 15.5 % (marked as 5.7 wt% CNTs/Epoxy, 10.9 wt% CNTs/Epoxy and 15.5 wt% CNTs/Epoxy), respectively. The CNT with an outer diameter of 4.7 Å and aspect ratio of 9.06 was used in the study. The CNTs were embedded freely into the composites, i.e. without covalent bonds between the CNTs and the epoxy matrix. The composite models with the same dimension of 43.7 Å×43.7 Å×43.7 Å were built to avoid size effect. Molecular structures of DGEBA, DDM and the CNT are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Molecular structures of compositions used in the simulation: (a) DGEBA, (b) DDM and (c) CNT. (Carbon and hydrogen atoms are shown in cyan and white color, respectively.)

All the MD simulations were conducted using the Materials Studio (Accelrys Inc.) software. COMPASS force-field was used [21, 22]. The non-bond interactions with a cut-off distance of 12.5 Å, including van der Waals and electronic static forces were applied. The atom based approach was used for the van der Waals force while the Ewald approach for the electronic static force.

The composites with an identical conversion of 90 % were finally obtained in the simulation [23]. Periodic boundary conditions were applied in all the three directions of the models. Snapshots of the composite models with three different contents of CNTs are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Snapshots of the composite models with three different contents of CNTs: (a) 5.7 wt% CNTs/Epoxy, (b) 10.9 wt% CNTs/Epoxy and (c) 15.5 wt% CNTs/Epoxy

2.2 Simulation procedure

After the initial microstructure of the composites models generated, geometric optimization of 5000 steps and the MD simulation using the ensembles of the constant number of particles, constant volume and constant temperature (NVT) was conducted. Then a short time-step dynamics from 280 K to 600 K, which was supposed to far beyond the T_g , was performed to relax the polymer chains.

In order to simulate the thermal performance of the composites in a kinetic process, the composites were cooled stepwise from 600 K to 280 K with a step-size of 20 K. The MD simulation using the ensemble of the constant number of particles, constant pressure and constant temperature (NPT) under a pressure of 0.1 MPa and an interval of 1 fs was conducted. The simulation was performed for 250 ps in each step, where the first 50 ps simulation was performed to relax the polymer chains, followed by 200 ps simulation to collect data for the dynamics analysis. Nose thermostat with Q ratio of 1.0 and Anderson barostat with cell time constant of 1.0 ps were adopted. Each subsequent simulation was started from the final configuration obtained at the preceding temperature.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the simulation, the uncertainty of every result was reduced by averaging five replicas for each composites model. Each of the composites was characterized using density, Connolly volume fraction, dynamical, and structural properties. For the neat epoxy resin and the 5.7 wt% CNTs/Epoxy, the models described in our previous work [23] were used for this analysis.

3.1 Density

In order to determine the T_g , results of densities from MD simulations at different temperatures for the composites with 5.7 wt%, 10.9 wt% and 15.5 wt% CNTs, compared with neat epoxy resin, are shown in Fig. 3. The glass transition in the composites can be observed as a change in the slope of the density vs. temperature plots. A linear decrease in density and a clear change in the slope of each curve can be observed. Temperatures corresponded to the kinks in the slopes were identified as the T_g , which occurred around 505.5 K, 454.4 K, 442.9 K and 445.7 K[23] for the investigated models, respectively.

Figure 3: Plots of density vs. temperature for the composites with different contents of CNTs. (Linear fitting of the data with an intersection, assuming linear relationship both below and above T_g .)

It can be seen that with the CNTs embedded into the epoxy, the density of the composites increased, and different CNT contents resulted in different densities. The density of the 5.7 wt% CNTs/Epoxy was the highest of all, while those of the composites with higher contents of CNTs were lower. The decrease in density indicates the presence of compressible interphase region at the interface between the CNTs and the epoxy matrix, since the CNTs were embedded freely into the composites.

With the CNTs embedded into the epoxy, T_g s of the composites increased remarkably at lower contents of CNTs. However, the T_g decreased with increasing contents of CNTs, and the T_g of the 15.5 wt% CNTs/Epoxy was even lower than that of the epoxy. Since the dimension of the CNT molecules used in the investigation was identical; the T_g change could be attributed to the increased CNT contents in the composites, i.e., increased compressible interphase region [12] between the CNTs and the epoxy matrix. With more CNT molecules embedded into the composites, more compressible interphase region at the interface between the CNTs and the epoxy matrix were produced. The composites were composed of the epoxy matrix, the CNTs and the interphase region between them, so that the T_g values were supposed to depend on the compressible interphase region greatly.

3.2 Connolly volume fraction

The main difference of the three composites was the CNT contents, corresponding to the interphase region between the CNTs and the epoxy. We attributed the differences in the density and the T_g s of the three composites to the differing amount of interphase region among them, which provides spaces for the epoxy chain segments to change their positions. The Connolly surface[24] was defined as the boundary between the Connolly probe and the atoms, thus the CVF can be used to characterize the space, which was believed to offer free volume for the motion of polymer chain segments, there thus to affect the T_g . Since the distribution of the matrix away from the CNTs in each composite was nearly the same, the CVF can qualitatively assess the amount of the interphase region. It affects the mobility of the epoxy chain segments, and associated with the T_g variations. The higher the CVF is, the greater the interphase region is. This resulted in a higher mobility of the epoxy chains, and hence a lower T_g value. The CVFs of the composites with 5.7 wt%、10.9 wt% and 15.5 wt% CNTs at different temperatures, compared with neat epoxy resin, are shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: The CVFs vs. temperature for the composites with different contents of CNTs.

From Fig. 4, the CVF of the composites monotonically decreased with the decreasing temperature, which meant that the space for the epoxy chain segments to change their positions was decreased. The CVF of the neat epoxy was higher than that of the 5.7 wt% CNTs/Epoxy and 10.9 wt% CNTs/Epoxy systems, indicating more space for the neat epoxy chain segments to change their positions. Meanwhile, the CVF of the 10.9 wt% CNTs/Epoxy and 15.5 wt% CNTs/Epoxy systems were much higher than the 5.7 wt% CNTs/Epoxy. The composites containing higher contents of CNTs had a larger volume fraction of interphase region, which was soft and compressible, compared with the cross-linked epoxy matrix region that was unaffected by the presence of the CNTs. This observation was consistent with the supposition that the increasing CNT molecules increased the interphase region between the CNTs and the epoxy, which resulted in more space for the epoxy chain segments to change their positions. The results were consistent with the density analysis of Fig. 3.

3.3 Mean squared displacement (MSD)

In the simulation, the epoxy matrices of the composites were identical in chemical composition and the extent of reaction conversion. The property variations between the composites arose only because of the differences in the contents of CNTs. Given the differences in T_g , it is instructive to analyze the mobility of the epoxy chain segments as a function of temperature, which can be characterized by MSD.

In the epoxy matrix composites, motion of the epoxy chain segments is affected by the CNTs significantly. So that the T_g value correlates well with the segmental mobility of the epoxy chains and the CNTs contents. The MSDs of all atoms in the composites with 5.7 wt%、10.9 wt% and 15.5 wt% CNTs, compared with neat epoxy resin, are plotted in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Plots of MSDs vs. temperature.

(Nonlinear relationship of the MSD vs. temperature was obtained by curve fitting based on the data, and an intersection was determined based on the two tangent lines at the initial and final points which corresponding to the glass transition of the composites.)

According to Fig. 5, the MSD of all atoms in the models increased exponentially with temperature. The intersections of linear fits of the calculated data at the initial and final points were around 514.9 K, 504.3 K and 489.3 K, respectively, compared with 497.6 K for the neat epoxy, which corresponding to the occurrence of glass transition.

The presence of the compressible interphase region in the composites with different contents of CNTs was expected to make significant differences in the mobility of the epoxy chain segments. The motion of the atoms and the mobility of the chain segments decreased sharply with the embedding of CNTs, resulted in a higher T_g . However, for the 15.5 wt% CNTs/Epoxy, the compressible interphase region between the CNTs and the epoxy increased greatly. The retardant on the motion of atoms in the epoxy and the mobility of the chain segments was less effectively due to the larger CVFs, resulted in decreased T_g . The T_g values calculated from the MSDs vs. temperature relationship were consistent with that corresponded to the densities.

Fig. 6 shows the MSDs of the nitrogen, the hydroxyl oxygen, the bridge oxygen and the epoxy oxygen (existed in the epoxy resin fragments that were not reacted with the harder fragments yet) atoms of the matrix in different systems at temperatures of below and above the T_g , respectively. It can be used to characterize the diffusivity of the atoms.

Fig. 6: MSD plots for (a) the nitrogen, (b) the hydroxyl oxygen, (c) the bridge oxygen and (d) the epoxy oxygen atoms of the matrix in the composites with different contents of CNTs at different temperatures.

Size of the CNTs is comparable with the polymer chain segments so that it can pin or hinder the mobility of segments or atoms in the matrix. When different contents of CNTs embedded into the composites, the diffusivity of the atoms in matrix would be interfered significantly. With the CNT contents increasing from 5.7 wt% to 15.5 wt%, the MSDs as well as the diffusivity of the atoms increased.

3.4 Radial distribution function (RDF)

To investigate the effect of CNT contents on the structural environment at the interface between the CNTs and the epoxy, the RDF was calculated between the CNTs and four atoms in the epoxy matrix: nitrogen, hydroxyl oxygen, bridge oxygen and epoxy oxygen at 400 K and 540 K, and shown in Fig. 7.

Figure7: RDFs between (a) the nitrogen, (b) the hydroxyl oxygen, (c) the bridge oxygen and (d) the epoxy oxygen atoms of the matrix and CNT carbons at different temperatures in the composites with different contents of CNTs.

For the nitrogen atoms, the similar curves of the RDF indicated that the structural conformation of the chain segments contained nitrogen atom around the CNTs in the composites was almost not changed with CNT contents at 400 K and 540 K, the distances between the nitrogen atoms and the CNTs are also almost the same. However, since the first RDF peak of the 10.9 wt% CNTs/Epoxy was beyond that of other systems at ~ 6.3 Å, a larger amount of the chain segments contained nitrogen atom around the CNTs could be deduced.

For the hydroxyl oxygen atoms, these distances were also almost the same. But the RDF curves are more distinguishable, indicating the differential distributions of the fragments. As the contents of CNTs increased from 5.7 wt% to 15.5 wt% in the composites, the distance of the chain segments contained hydroxyl oxygen atom around the CNTs reduced in the region of 8.0 Å to 15 Å. That's to say, the increasing CNT contents keep the chain segments contained hydroxyl oxygen atom away from the CNTs, resulted in larger interphase region.

For the bridge oxygen atoms, the RDF curves were identical, where the minima of first peaks for all the systems were approximately at 7.5 Å. For the 400 K-5.7 wt% CNTs/Epoxy and 540 K-5.7 wt% CNTs/Epoxy systems, the second minimum was at ~ 11.2 Å; while it was at ~ 12.0 Å for others. It indicated that the bridge oxygen containing segments were more closely to the CNTs in the 5.7 wt% CNTs/Epoxy, and the relative sharp peaks at ~ 11.2 Å indicated the relative closely surrounding.

For the epoxy oxygen atoms, the RDF curves were much more apart from each other, indicating completely different distributions of the segments in different systems. The epoxy bridge oxygen containing segments around the CNTs increased with the increasing contents of CNTs in the

composites. Slight peaks with the minima at approximately 6.8 Å appeared in the 5.7 wt% CNTs/Epoxy and 10.9 wt% CNTs/Epoxy systems, while there was no noticeable peak in the 15.5 wt% CNTs/Epoxy. It indicated that the interaction between the epoxy oxygen atoms of the matrix and the CNT carbons in previous two systems was more attractive than that in the 15.5 wt% CNTs/Epoxy. It was consistent with the statement that the stronger the interaction between the CNTs and the matrix is, the higher the T_g is.

4 CONCLUSIONS

With CNTs embedded into the epoxy, T_g s of the CNTs/epoxy composites increased remarkably at low CNT contents. However, it decreased with the CNT contents increasing from 5.7 wt% to 15.5 wt%. Namely, the glass transition of the composites was strongly affected by the CNT contents. The MSD and RDF analysis of the specific atoms indicated that more compressible interphase region was produced with increasing contents of CNTs, which made it much easier for the atoms to move, and the embedded CNTs changed the segmental distributions greatly. It suggested that the poor interfacial interactions at the interface of CNTs and the epoxy lead to a more compressible interphase region between the CNTs and the bulk matrix.

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